

less dehydrated by heating to 80° without any appreciable decomposition. They liberate two equivalents of iodine per silver atom in the molecule from acidified KI solution. The molecular conductivity of the nitrate at 20° was found to be 518 ohms^{-2} (approx.) at infinite dilution. This agrees well with values for trivalent complex ions. Unlike the complex salts of bivalent silver, which are all paramagnetic like those of bivalent copper, the complex silver (Ag^{III}) ethylene-dibiguamide salts are all diamagnetic.

The occurrence of silver in a state of oxidation, higher than what corresponds to Ag_2O or Ag_2O_2 , is not altogether unknown. Luther and Pokorny (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1908, **57**, 299) have shown that the peroxide of silver formed by electrolytic oxidation of a silver anode in sulphuric acid and the so-called peroxy-nitrate and other similar salts of silver, prepared by electrolytic oxidation of neutral solutions of silver salts, consist essentially of the peroxide Ag_2O_2 with occluded or adsorbed silver salts in the latter case. Silver therefore behaves in this case as a trivalent element, if, of course, the formation of a ring compound or a chain of oxygen atoms be excluded.

Higson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **119**, 2048), by the action of a solution of sodium persulphate on metallic silver as well as on a solution of silver nitrate in the cold, obtained a product which consisted of a peroxide of the approximate composition, Ag_3O_4 .

Recently Malatesta (*Gazzetta*, 1941, **71**, 580) has reported the preparation of acid sodium salts of a complex silver telluric acid, $\text{Na}_6\text{H}_3 [\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}_2(\text{TeO}_6)_2]$ and $\text{Na}_7\text{H}_2 [\text{Ag}^{\text{III}}(\text{TeO}_6)_2]$, in which the silver atom serves as the centre of the anionic complex. As, owing to war conditions, the original paper is not available here, we are not in a position to discuss about the nature and stability of this complex salt.

The electronic configuration of a trivalent silver atom should resemble that of bivalent nickel and palladium, just as bivalent silver is analogous to bivalent copper in its outer electronic structure. Hence a quadri-covalent complex of trivalent silver should be, as has been actually found, diamagnetic in character, if the co-ordination bonds be of the hybrid planar $d-s-p^2$ type as in the corresponding bivalent nickel and palladium complexes. In fact, this serves as a confirmation of trivalency of silver in these complex salts. This is apparent from the electronic structures in the outermost levels of uni-, bi- and trivalent silver ions and those of bi- and trivalent silver complexes as shown below.

In silver the first three quantum levels as well as $4s$ and $4p$ levels representing the krypton core, are completely filled up with electrons and are not shown in the above scheme.

That a trivalent silver atom gives a co-ordination number of four and not six, which is characteristic of a large number of other trivalent ions, is perfectly in keeping with its position between copper and gold in the same group of the Periodic Table. A trivalent gold, as is well known, always forms a quadri-covalent complex; and Burawoy, Gibson, Hampson and Powell (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1690) have shown by crystallographic examination that diethyl monobromogold, $(C_2H_5)_2AuBr$, gives a square planar structure by polymerisation. There is therefore nothing unusual in that the silver atom shows the character of both copper and gold, becoming uni-, bi- and trivalent respectively as well as quadri-covalent in its complexes for the latter two cases.

EXPERIMENTAL

Silver Ethylene-dibiguanidinium Sulphate.—A solution of 0.3 g. of silver sulphate in 60 c.c. of water was mixed with a solution of 1 g. of ethylene-dibiguanide sulphate in 200 c.c. water. The mixture was cooled and treated with 1 g. of potassium persulphate dissolved in a little water. This was then diluted to about 550 c.c. and kept in the cold for about 18 hours with occasional stirring. A beautiful silky crystalline precipitate of red colour gradually separated from the solution. This was filtered, washed with cold water and then dried on a porous plate. The crystals were kept over $CaCl_2$ in a desiccator in the cold.

The substance is sparingly soluble in water. In the solid state it can be heated to 80° without appreciable decomposition. A solution of the pure substance in water or dilute sulphuric acid can be heated on the water-bath without any detectable change. In concentrated sulphuric acid it dissolves to form a red solution. The salt keeps unchanged at ordinary temperature for a pretty long time. On qualitative examination the substance was found to be free from persulphate. {Found: C, 13.60; H, 4.30; N, 26.50, 26.40, 26.30; Ag, 19.86, 19.70, 19.60; SO_4 , 27.0, 26.40, 26.25; H_2O (by loss at 80°), 10.40 per cent}. 0.0954 G. of the substance liberated 6.9×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag as Ag^{III} , 19.83; 0.1592 g. of the substance liberated 11.475×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 19.75; 0.1918 g. of the substance liberated 7.0 c.c. of $N/10$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 19.70 per cent. [$Ag^{III}En(BigH^+)_2$](SO_4) $_{1.25}$, 3.5 H_2O requires C, 13.31; H, 4.44; N, 25.88; Ag, 19.96; SO_4 , 26.61; H_2O , 11.65 per cent. $En(BigH)_2 = C_6N_{10}H_{18}$ = a molecule of ethylene-dibiguanide.

It gave a diamagnetic susceptibility of $\chi_g = -0.394 \times 10^{-6}$.

The Base.—The complex sulphate was decomposed with cold 15% solution of sodium hydroxide or potassium hydroxide. The product was washed by decantation with cold alkaline water (containing a few drops of $N-NaOH$ or KOH) till free from sulphate and then finally with cold water. It forms violet-red microcrystalline mass resembling permanganate in colour. This was dried as described above.

The base is sparingly soluble in water and reacts strongly alkaline to litmus. It decomposes on heating with water.

Found: N, 32.10, 31.95, 32.20; Ag, 24.45, 24.20, 24.40; 0.2260 g. of the substance liberated 20×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 24.35; 0.1343 g. liberated 10.95×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 22.45; 0.1174 g. liberated 9.35×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 21.85%. [$Ag^{III}En(BigH^+)_2$](OH) $_3$, 3 H_2O requires N, 31.75; Ag, 24.49 per cent.

The last two samples show some sign of reduction.

The mass susceptibility, $\chi_g = -0.393 \times 10^{-6}$.

The Nitrate.—This was prepared by treating the moist base with a cold solution of $N\text{-HNO}_3$. The violet-red base changed into orange-red crystals of the nitrate. These were recrystallised from hot dilute nitric acid (2*N*). The crystals were washed with cold water containing a few drops of nitric acid and then dried as in the previous cases.

The nitrate is moderately soluble in water, the solution decomposes on boiling with decolourisation. It can be boiled in dilute nitric acid solution without any noticeable change.

Found: C, 13.80; H, 3.64, N (total), 35.0, 35.0, 35.0; Ag, 20.75, 20.34, 20.52 per cent. NO_3 (by nitron), 36.0; 0.1148 g. of the substance liberated 8.6×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 20.55; 0.1504 g. liberated 11.25×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 20.50; 0.1311 g. liberated 10.10×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 20.65 per cent. [$\text{Ag}^{\text{III}} \text{En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2$] (NO_3)₃ requires C, 13.80; H, 3.07; N (total), 34.87; Ag 20.69; NO_3 , 35.63 per cent.

Magnetic susceptibility, $\chi_g = -0.402 \times 10^{-6}$.

Molecular conductivity

$t = 20^\circ$.

ν (dilution in g. mol. per litre) ...	488	976	1952	3904
μ_v ...	362.5	397.0	429.8	467.8
μ_∞ (by extrapolation) =	518.0 approx.			

The Perchlorate.—This was prepared by treating the moist base with cold 60% perchloric acid solution, added drop by drop, till the violet-red base changed completely into the dark red shining crystals of the perchlorate. The mixture was cooled strongly in ice. The crystals were filtered on the pump and dried on a porous plate. These were kept as usual in the cold over CaCl_2 in a desiccator. The substance is highly soluble in water.

Found: N, 21.35; Ag, 16.70, 16.40; ClO_4 , 43.40; 0.2675 g. of the substance liberated 16.20×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 16.75; 0.1635 g. liberated 9.90×1.0166 c.c. of $N/20$ iodine; Ag^{III} , 16.60 per cent. [$\text{Ag}^{\text{III}} \text{En}(\text{BigH}^+)_2$] (ClO_4)₃, 1.5 H_2O requires N, 21.16; Ag, 16.31; ClO_4 , 45.10 per cent.

The base, on treatment with cold NH_4HF_2 solution, gave an orange-yellow fluoride which, however, readily lost HF when removed from the solution and turned violet-red due to more or less complete reformation of the base.

With cold 2*N*-HCl the base similarly formed an orange-red chloride, which readily decomposed into white silver chloride.

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